

PROPERTIES OF BOREL SETS

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Annotation: This article the properties of sets F_σ and G_δ , which are Borel sets, in topological spaces were studied and the following results were obtained:

- a) Preimage of the set F_σ (resp. G_δ) under the continuous mapping is also the set F_σ (resp. G_δ);
- b) The image of the set G_δ under the continuous mapping is not the set G_δ ;
- c) The image of the set G_δ under the open mapping is not the set G_δ ;
- d) The sets F_σ and G_δ are preserved under the Cartesian product.

Keywords: topological space, Cartesian product, Tixonov topology, continuous mapping, Borel sets, G_δ - sets, F_σ – sets.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Borel to'plamlari bo'lgan F_σ va G_δ to'plamlarning topologik fazolardagi xossalari o'rganildi va quyidagi muhim natjalar olindi:

- a) F_σ (mos ravishda G_δ) to'planning uzluksiz akslantirishdagi proobrazi yana F_σ (mos ravishda G_δ) to'plam bo'ladi;
- b) G_δ to'planning uzluksiz akslantirishdagi obrazi G_δ to'plam bo'lmaydi;
- c) G_δ to'planning ochiq akslantirishdagi obrazi G_δ to'plam bo'lmaydi;
- d) F_σ va G_δ to'plamlar to'g'ri ko'paytmada saqlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: topologik fazo, to'g'ri ko'paytma, Tixonov topologiyasi, uzluksiz akslantirish, Borel to'plamlari, G_δ -to'plamlar, F_σ – to'plamlar.

Relevance of the topic: Let's see the direct (right) Cartesian product of sets $\prod X_\alpha$ an arbitrary number. There are X_α multiple for every $\alpha \in A$ and A the power of sets might be infinite. X_α is topologic space for every $\alpha \in A$. In $\prod X_\alpha$ multiple, we will find a weak topology, there are every $P_\alpha : \prod X_\alpha \rightarrow X_\alpha$ projection is constant in this topology. There are P_α projection is a place coordinate to x_α for each $x = (x_\alpha)$, ($\alpha \in A \in \prod X_\alpha$) point. This topology is called topology in product or Tixonov topology.

All subsets of a topological space X that can be obtained from open subsets of X , or what is the same from closed subsets of X , by taking countable unions and intersections as well as complements, are from the topological point of view of a particularly regular form, and the family of those sets is worth studying. By the family of Borel sets in a topological space X we mean the smallest family φ of subsets of X satisfying the following conditions:

(BS1) The family φ contains all open subsets of X .

(BS2) If $A \in \varphi$, then $X \setminus A \in \varphi$.

(BS3) If $A_i \in \varphi$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, then $\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \in \varphi$.

The fact that there exists a smallest family φ satisfying the above conditions follows from the simple observation that the family of all subsets of X satisfies (BS1)–(BS3) and that for any collection of families satisfying (BS1)–(BS3), the common part of all families in the collection is a family satisfying those conditions. Hence, the family of Borel sets in X could be as well defined to be the common part of all families φ satisfying (BS1)–(BS3).

Let us note that in the definition of Borel sets condition (BS1) can be replaced by (BS1'). The family φ contains all closed subsets of X ,

and condition (BS3) can be replaced by (BS3'). If $A_i \in \varphi$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, then

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \in \varphi.$$

Indeed, the conjunction of (BS1') and (BS2) is equivalent to the conjunction of (BS1) and (BS2), and the conjunction of (BS2) and (BS3') is equivalent to the conjunction of (BS2) and (BS3).

The most common Borel sets, besides open sets and closed sets, are countable unions of closed sets and countable intersections of open sets – the former are called F_σ -sets and the latter G_δ -sets. Clearly the complement of an F_σ -set is a G_δ -set and vice versa.

1. Definition. The countable intersections of open sets is called G_δ -sets.

The unions of two G_δ -sets is again a G_δ -set. Clearly a countable intersection of G_δ -sets is again a G_δ -set. The set of all rationals is an F_σ -set in $\mathbb{R}$; the fact that it is not a G_δ -set is not so obvious.

Let's given $G_\delta : K = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i, \forall i \in N, S_i$ - open sets.

1. Theorem. Let's given $f : X \rightarrow Y$ continuous mapping. If G_δ -set is in $K \subset Y$, in this case $f^{-1}(K) \subset X$ set is G_δ -set in X .

Proof. It was given in $K = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i \subset Y. f^{-1}(K) = f^{-1}(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} f^{-1}(S_i). f^{-1}(S_i) \subset X$ is closed set for f mapping was continuous, for $i \in N$. So, $f^{-1}(K)$ set was G_δ -set.

1. Proposition. The countable intersection of closed sets in X metric space is called G_δ -set.

Proof. a) F set is an every nonempty closed part set of (X, ρ) metric space we will look at spheric neighbourhoods of F set $U_n = O(F, \frac{1}{n})$ for every $n=1,2,..$ uchun $F \subseteq U_n$. So,

$$F \subseteq \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} U_n.$$

b) We will show opposite connection. It is $x \in \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} U_n$. Then, it is $\rho(x, F) < \frac{1}{n}$ for each of $n=1,2,\dots$. It is clearly seen that x point is point of contact of F sets. We have $x \in F$ because of closed F set. It is seen from a) and b) it is $F = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} U_n$. F set is G_δ set at there. Proposition was proved.

1. Example. The set of natural number is $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n, \dots\}$ in axis of numbers. The set of natural numbers is closed in real numbers. As for as proposition N set G_δ -set.

2. Example. $Z = \{\dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ is the set of all whole numbers. G_δ -set in order to close in real numbers.

3. Example. $\mathfrak{I}$ - is the set of all irrational numbers. This is G_δ -kind of set. Indeed, $r \in Q$ $U_r = \mathfrak{I} \setminus \{r\}$ - is open set for every $r \in Q$. Q -is the set of all rational numbers. So, $\mathfrak{I} = \bigcap \{U_r : r \in Q\}$.

This example show that there are also G_δ -kind of set apart from closed part set in the axis of numbers. Because, there is not $\mathfrak{I}$ - closed part of set of irrational numbers in the axis of numbers..

2. Proposition. If M set is G_δ -set, its continuous image can not be G_δ -set.

For example. There are closed set in $y = \frac{1}{x}$ ($x \neq 0$), hyperbola R^2 because its fill is open. If we get an optional x point in $R^2 \setminus \left\{ \frac{1}{x} \right\}$ there is its surroundings. If we project the graph to x axi, it will be $\Pi(x, y) = x$. The project is continuous, it will be, $(-\infty, 0) \cup (0, \infty)$. This is open set. So, the continuous image of G_δ -sets is not G_δ - set.

1. Result. G_δ -set which is in mapping image is not G_δ -set.

It can be clearly seen from $y = \frac{1}{x}$, if we project the graph to x axi, the project will be open mapping. It is seen that G_δ -set cannot save in open mapping.

2. Result. G_δ -set may not be saved in single value mapping.

We can see the proof of this abovementioned example.

If we have $G_\delta : K = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i$, S_i -open set, every $i \in N$, in topologic space.

2. Theorem. G_δ – set was saved under the Cartesian product.

Proof. $K = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i$, S_i - open sets and $A = \bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} A_j$, A_j - open sets.

$K \times A = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i \times \bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} A_j = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} (S_i \times A_j) \right)$ equality is appropriate.

3. Result. If $K \subset X$ set in the Cartesian product is G_δ – kind of set, then K^n set will be also G_δ – kind of set.

2. Definition. The union of closed sets in counting numbers called F_σ – set.

The joint of F_σ – sets is G_δ – set and opposite of this. The intersection of F_σ – set will be again F_σ – set. The counting union of F_σ – set will be F_σ – set.

In fact, if $E = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} E_i$ and $F = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} F_j$, E_i va F_j are closed sets at there, then

$E \cap F = \bigcup_{i,j=1}^{\infty} (E_i \cap F_j)$, So, $E \cap F$ set F_σ – set.

We have $F_\sigma : M = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i$, U_i – closed sets $i \in N$.

3. Theorem: $f : X \rightarrow Y$ it is given continuous mapping. If $M \subset Y$ is F_σ – then $f^{-1}(M) \subset X$ set is F_σ – set in X .

Proof. There is $M = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i \subset Y$. $f^{-1}(M) = f^{-1}\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i\right) = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} f^{-1}(U_i)$ is. $f^{-1}(U_i) \subset X$ is open set because f mapping is continuous for optional $i \in N$. So, $f^{-1}(M)$ set is F_σ – set.

3. Proposition. F_σ – set is the union of open sets under countable in X metric space.

Proof. U set is an optional unempty part of set in (X, ρ) metric space. Then, in

(X, ρ) , $X \setminus U = F$ is not empty closed part of set. As for as first defination, we can write

$$F \text{ as } F = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} U_n . U_n \text{ set is open set at } (X, \rho) U = X \setminus F = X \setminus \left(\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} U_n \right) = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} (X \setminus U_n) = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n , F_{\sigma} -$$

set come from U set. Confirmation was proved.

4. Example. Q is the set of all rational number in the real numbers. This is F_{σ} - set. Indeed, $Q = \bigcup \{ \{r\} : r \in Q \}$ in the real numbers, $\{r\}$ closed set is the union of countable. But, whether Q – the set of rational numbers is or not open in the real numbers.

We have $F_{\sigma} : M = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i$, U_i – closed sets $i \in N$, topologic space.

4. Proposition. F_{σ} – set is preserved in the Cartesion product.

Proof. 1) $M = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i$, U_i – closed sets and $N = \bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} V_j$, V_j – closed sets.

$$M \times N = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} U_i \times \bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} V_j = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} (U_i \times V_j) \right) \text{ equality is appropriate.}$$

4. Result. If $M \subset X$ set is F_{σ} – kind of set in the Cartesion product, then M^n set is also F_{σ} – kind of set.

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